

Iso-Thiocyanate Derivatives of Diarylthallium(III) Cation and their Microbiocidal Propensities

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Hitherto unknown *iso*-thiocyanate derivatives of diarylthallium(III) cation have been synthesised in almost quantitative yields by the interaction of diarylthallium(III) chloride and ammonium thiocyanate in pyridine-water (1 : 1) mixture. Infrared data in support of the *iso*-structure are presented. The microbiocidal properties of the *iso*-thiocyanate derivatives have been investigated, and that are shown to possess superior combating properties against the test pathogenic fungi and bacteria than other reported derivatives of the diarylthallium(III) cation.

SINCE the report of Goddard¹ on dimethylthallium(III) thiocyanate synthesis in 1921, organothallium(III) thiocyanates does not appear to have attracted the attention of chemists. Recently the diarylthallium(III) cation has been reported² to possess excellent microbiocidal properties. Compounds containing the thiocyanate group are also known to exhibit similar properties. In the present paper the synthesis and characterisation of hitherto unknown diarylthallium(III) *iso*-thiocyanates (aryl=phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl or *p*-tolyl) have been reported.

The compounds have also been evaluated for their microbiocidal properties against some pathogenic fungi and bacteria.

Experimental

Diarylthallium(III) chloride derivatives were synthesised according to literature methods^{3,4}. All chemicals used in the present work were Analar or G. R. grades (B. D. H. or E. Merck).

The title compounds were obtained in almost quantitative yield by the mixing a solution of diarylthallium(III) chloride (1 m mole) in 50 ml of 1 : 1 pyridine-water mixture with a concentrated aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate (5 m mole). The mixture was stirred for an hour and the precipitated diarylthallium(III) thiocyanate was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and finally with diethyl ether. The compounds were dried at 90°. The melting points, analytical data and the infrared active anionic absorptions of the newly synthesised compounds are collected in Table-1. Thallium was estimated as Tl_2CrO_4 from H_2SO_4 - HNO_3 digested samples⁵.

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The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions was measured at 35° in dimethyl formamide using Philips Conductivity bridge type PR 9500 having dip type conductivity cell. Due to the insolubility of the compounds in suitable solvents, molecular weight could not be determined either cryoscopically or by the Rast method.

The infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol-mull were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} using a Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer model 521 (accuracy $\pm 5 cm^{-1}$).

Microbiocidal tests

Antimicrobial activities of the compounds indicated earlier² are described here. Microorganisms studied included (a) *Colletotrichum falcatum* Went (the causal organism of red rot disease of sugarcane which alone causes national loss to the tune of several crores annually), (b) *Candida albicans* (Robin) Berkhout, *Cryptococcus neoformans* (Sanfelie) Vuillemin, *Microsporium canis* Bodin, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (Robin) Blanchard and *Aspergillus niger* (all fungi) which are responsible for a large number of mammalian diseases.

The bacterial test species were *Bacillus subtilis* Cohn emnd. Prazmowski, *Staphylococcus aureus* Rosenbach, *Salmonella typhi* Warren & Scott, *Escherichia coli* (Migula) Castellani and Chalmers which are also mammalian pathogens causing various diseases.

Concentration of diarylthallium(III) *iso*-thiocyanates required for suppression of visual growth of *C. falcatum* was determined by poisoned food technique and per cent inhibition calculated

following the equation of Vincent⁶. Effective dose for 50% inhibition (ED 50) of the fungal growth was thus determined⁷. For all the remaining pathogens minimum inhibitory concentration was determined according to methods employed by Bajpai and Bajpai⁸ upto a maximum of 100 µg/ml.

Results and Discussion

The compounds are dirty white crystalline solids, insoluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, diethyl ether etc. but dissolve appreciably in pyridine, dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. They are thermally stable at room temperature and insensitive to atmospheric moisture and air but decompose when heated to melting points. Molar conductance recorded was in the range of 60.10-91.72 ohm⁻¹ cm² moles⁻¹, indicating 1 : 1 electrolyte character of the compounds. In want of molecular weight data, related studies could not be undertaken.

Various infrared absorptions associated with aromatic group were observed at the positions reported in one of our earlier publications⁹, are not listed here. The absorptions related with various fundamental modes of vibration of *iso*-thiocyanate group are depicted in the last column of the Table-1. The linear *iso*-thiocyanate is reported to give three fundamental modes of vibration in the recorded infrared range of this study, out of which most important is located in the range 2100-2000 cm⁻¹ and assigned to asymmetric -NCS stretching mode¹⁰. In various *iso*-thiocyanates^{11,12} this mode of vibration is reported at 2075±35 cm⁻¹ (ν asymmetric NCS in solid potassium *iso*-thiocyanate¹⁶ 2053 cm⁻¹), whereas the corresponding vibration of

thiocyanate (SCN) appears at 2155±15 cm⁻¹. In the present investigation this absorption appears as a band of very strong intensity, slightly broader in shape at 2040±15 cm⁻¹ which appears closer to the *iso*-form than the normal thiocyanate. The position, intensity and shape of this absorption band is used for distinguishing between the *iso* and normal forms¹³⁻¹⁵. Conductance data also support this conclusion.

Two other absorptions of weak to very weak intensity located at 905±3 cm⁻¹ and 480±2 cm⁻¹ are assigned to symmetric NCS stretching and NCS bending modes respectively (cf. values reported for trimethyl lead *iso*-thiocyanate by Thayer and Strommen¹⁰).

Antimicrobial activities of the compounds are listed in Table-2.

All the test compounds were effective against *C. falcatum* but *iso*-thiocyanates of diarylthallium-(III) cation possessed significantly superior efficacy. *C. albicans*, *C. neoformans* and *A. niger* remained unchecked upto maximum test level of the compounds, however, a concentration range of 3.125 to 25 µg/ml completely arrested growth of *T. mentagrophytes* and *M. canis*.

In general, the compounds depicted better bactericidal properties as growth of all the test bacteria could be controlled at 3.125-25 µg/ml. *iso*-thiocyanate derivatives of diarylthallium(III) species showed comparatively better microbiocidal efficacy than diphenylthallium(III) chloride included in the Table-2 for comparison. Among the test *iso*-thiocyanates, *di-m*-tolylthallium (III) *iso*-thiocyanate expressed superior microbiocidal properties.

TABLE-1 EXPERIMENTAL DATA OF DIARYLTHALLIUM(III) *ISO*-THIOCYANATE

Aryl group	m.p. (°C)	Percent found (calcd.)				IR absorptions		
		Tl	C	H	N	νNCS (asym)	νNCS (sym)	νNCS (bending)
Phenyl	273-74	48.9 (49.0)	37.2 (37.5)	2.2 (2.4)	3.4 (3.4)	2025 vs	902 w	482 vw
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	205	46.2 (45.9)	40.2 (40.5)	2.9 (3.1)	3.5 (3.1)	2055 vs	908 vw	478 vw
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	208	46.1 (45.9)	39.9 (40.5)	2.9 (3.1)	3.4 (3.1)	2030 vs	908 w	482 vw
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	215-18	46.3 (45.9)	40.1 (40.5)	3.3 (3.1)	3.5 (3.1)	2045 vs	904 vw	480 vw

v = very, s = strong, and w = weak.

TABLE-2. MICROBICIDAL PROPERTIES OF DIARYLTHALLIUM(III) *ISO*-THIOCYANATE (VALUES REPRESENT MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION EXPRESSED IN µg/ml)

Aryl	Fungi						Bacteria			
	<i>C. falcatum</i> (E.D. 53 id ppm)	<i>G. olbicans</i>	<i>C. neoformans</i>	<i>T. metagrophytes</i>	<i>M. canis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Phenyl	9.2	> 100	> 100	12.5	12.5	> 100	3.125	12.50	> 100	25.0
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	< 1	> 100	> 100	6.50	25	> 100	6.250	12.50	25	25.0
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	< 1	> 100	> 100	6.25	25	> 100	3.125	6.25	12.5	12.5
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	< 1	> 100	> 100	6.25	3.125	> 100	6.250	12.50	25	12.5
Ph ₂ Tl(III)Cl	13.1	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	3.125	12.50	> 100	> 100

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